

INSTITUTIONAL FACTORS AND USE OF INSTITUTIONAL REPOSITORIES BY POSTGRADUATE STUDENTS IN THREE UNIVERSITIES IN SOUTHWESTERN NIGERIA

By

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Abstract

This study explores the relationship between Institutional Factors (IFs) and use of Institutional Repositories (IRs) by postgraduate students in three universities in South western, Nigeria. The study adopted the descriptive survey research design of the correlational types, the population was 16,511 postgraduate students in University of Ibadan, Ibadan, Oyo State, Covenant University, Ota, Ogun State and Obafemi Awolowo University, Ile-Ife, Osun State. A two-stage sampling technique was used to select a sample of 345 postgraduate students. The data were collected through a questionnaire and analysed using the descriptive and inferential statistics. The results indicated that journals were the most frequently used information resource and the primary purpose for accessing IRs included assignment completion, citation of scholarly work and sourcing materials for research. There was also a significant relationship between IFs and IRs usage ($r = 0.447$, $P < 0.05$). However, institutional factors such as robust technical support, adequate infrastructure, sufficient funding and clear policies contribute significantly to the effectiveness and use of these repositories by postgraduate students. Therefore, universities should enhance institutional support, infrastructure, funding and policies to improve students' use of institutional repositories.

Keywords: Institutional factors, Use of institutional repositories, Postgraduate students, Southwestern universities

Introduction

Universities, as institutions of higher learning, place great emphasis on research output as one of their primary functions, alongside teaching and community development. The quality and quantity of research produced in a university is a key metric used to determine its worth and relevance. Ensuring that a university remains relevant and contributes positively to the development of its immediate environment and the world at large requires a strong focus on managing and disseminating the research output generated by its postgraduate students and academic staff. However, the traditional method of storing the research outputs of a university in physical libraries, using print formats is often insufficient in meeting the needs of modern academia.

This is why the need for institutional repositories within universities becomes crucial. Institutional repositories are digital archives that collect, preserve; and provide access to the intellectual and creative output of a university's community. According to Musa, Musa and Aliyu (2014), an institutional repository is a database for preserving the local content of an academic institution. Local content such as research publications, conference proceedings and inaugural lectures generated in an institution of higher learning can be digitised and kept in the university's repositories. By establishing these repositories, universities can increase the visibility and impact of their research, ensuring the long-term preservation and archiving of their scholarly works. It also enables collaboration and sharing among researchers, while, showcasing their institutional strengths.

Existing literature suggests that the successful adoption and use of institutional repositories within universities are influenced by a combination of factors, these can include institutional factors, awareness and technical expertise of students and researchers. According to Tony-Okereke (2021), institutional factors encompass a range of conditions in the university environment that may affect the use of IRs. These include factors such as proximity to the library, availability of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) laboratories, cost of access, institutional policies governing IR use, academic culture; among Ivwighreghweta and Igere (2014) emphasised that in developing countries, there are numerous institutional factors that determine the adoption and use of the internet, which in turn could impact the level of utilisation of institutional repositories for research purposes. These institutional factors include inadequate infrastructure, lack of institutional policies on ICT resource development, technology supply problems, scarcity of human resources, educational challenges and economic constraints.

The implication is that the successful adoption and utilisation of institutional repositories within universities is dependent upon the presence of a supportive institutional environment. As such, factors such as accessibility to necessary infrastructure, availability of relevant policies, adequate human and financial resources and a culture that promotes the use of digital research platforms can all contribute to the effective use of institutional repositories by the university community.

Statement of the problem

Institutional repositories are databases that contribute to both the development of an institution and the world through its well-grounded research outputs. They platforms for scholars

to gather, communicate, disseminate and share their research findings with one another. The main purpose of institutional repositories is to create, store, manage; and preserve the institution's scholarly output and making them available to both a nation and the world at large through the internet. However, despite the benefits accrued to the use of institutional repositories (IRs) by students, studies have shown that most postgraduate students in universities in Southwestern Nigeria do not use institutional repositories optimally. This could be as a result of the lack of institutional factors in universities, lack of institutional factors such as infrastructure, policy, technical support and funding could impede the use of IRs in universities. This study, thus, examines institutional factors and use of institutional repositories by postgraduate students in three universities in Southwestern Nigeria.

Research Questions

The following research questions were answered in the study:

1. What are the types of information resources used in institutional repositories by postgraduate students in three universities in Southwestern Nigeria.?
2. What is the frequency of use of institutional repositories by postgraduate students in three universities in Southwestern Nigeria.?
3. What is the purpose of use of institutional repositories by postgraduate students in three universities in Southwestern Nigeria.?
4. What is the prevailing institutional factors in three universities in Southwestern Nigeria.?

Hypothesis

1. There is no significant relationship between institutional factors and use of institutional repositories by postgraduate students in three universities in Southwestern Nigeria

Literature review

In recent years, Institutional Repositories (IRs) have become a key part of academic systems, helping universities to collect, preserve and share their intellectual work. Originally, IRs are designed to showcase a university's research and boost its global visibility. They provide open access to scholarly work, help to meet funding bodies requirements and support teaching and learning activities (Xia, 2011). The use of IRs by students is influenced by a myriad of institutional factors, ranging from technological infrastructure and administrative support to the

overarching academic culture that promotes or hinders their use. Studies have shown that factors such as visibility and availability of training and technical support significantly impact students' adoption and effective use of IRs.

Saini (2018) noted that, the slow adoption and development of repositories in many developing countries are primarily due to the fact that many higher learning institutions are still in the process of establishing guiding principles and best practices in using IRs. Similarly, Ampong (2016) attributed the slow adoption and use of institutional repositories in African countries to institutional challenges such as lack of user awareness, poor user attitudes, unreliable electricity, inadequate policies, and issues with Internet access and cost. Mantikayan and Abdulgani (2018) averred that institutional factors like training, staff support, technical support and guidance, resources, awards, workload, research culture, tenure and promotion, financial awards, performance standards, peer and social recognition, and leadership factors like appreciation and orientation can influence students' research productivity.

Bamigbola and Adetimirin (2017) examined the level of awareness, frequency of use, preferred archiving method, purpose of use of IRs and challenges of use of IRs among lecturers in Nigeria. The findings revealed that majority of the lecturers were aware of IRs, they accessed materials from IRs on daily and weekly basis while they deposited their works into IR on annual and bi-annual basis. It was also revealed that lecturers preferred mediated archiving and they used materials from IRs to prepare lecture notes and research works. Fear of copyrights infringement, plagiarism and lack of awareness were major challenges of use of IRs.

In the same vein, Okoroma (2018) examined factors influencing use of institutional repositories in some Nigerian universities. This study employed a descriptive survey research design, using a self-developed structured questionnaire; multistage sampling procedure was used to select 751 staff members (436 males and 315 females) across various universities in Nigeria. The findings revealed that the development and maintenance of institutional repositories in Nigerian university libraries have been very slow and uneven, largely due to numerous institutional and external factors hindering their sustainability.

Similarly, Ogunsola and Oluyemi (2019) assessed institutional factors influencing internet use among postgraduate students in Nigerian universities. The influence of institutional factors (adequacy of computers in ICT centres; internet facilities and wireless access points; enabling Internet policy for students; administrative and technical support; conducive ICT

environment; reliable internet connectivity; provision of steady power supply; internet training for students; cost of accessing Internet and privacy concern) on the Internet use among 475 students' in three universities in South-west region of Nigeria. The findings revealed that cost of internet access contributed directly to daily Internet use of the respondents in two universities. Therefore, IFs do make significant contribution to the use of Internet by the respondents.

In the same vein, Tony-Okereke (2021) focused on IFs as determinants of 374 LIS lecturers' utilisation of electronic publications in library schools in 24 public universities in Nigeria. The results showed that there is a moderate positive relationship between computer skills and lecturers' utilisation of e-publications for research as well as a high positive relationship among institutional factors. Anenene, Alegbeleye; and Oyewole (2017) explored the factors influencing the adoption of Institutional Repositories (IRs) by 32 library staff in seven universities in South-west, Nigeria, focusing on the perspectives of library staff. The results revealed that majority of the respondents had a high level of awareness about IRs, held a favorable perception of them, found IRs to be easy to use and highly beneficial. The study also identified licensing agreements, deposit and withdrawal services, and issues related to copyright and intellectual property as key factors that could influence the adoption of IRs.

Ukwoma and Ngulube (2019) carried out a study to determine the main barriers to the use of IRs by 491 academics in five Nigerian universities and to suggest ways to improve their utilisation. The findings revealed that the primary barrier to use of IR included inadequate infrastructure, lack of awareness and sensitisation among academics, and insufficient technical skills. The authors recommended formulating institutional policies on repositories, increasing awareness among staff; and involving management in repository-related projects and emphasised the importance of collaboration between academic institutions' management and the academic community to ensure the successful use of institutional repositories.

Posigha and Idjai (2022) investigated the availability of IR policies guiding the development of IRs in Nigerian university libraries. The study highlighted several IR-related policies essential for the effective implementation and management of content in institutional repositories. It also identified various challenges faced by repository administrators and librarians, including lack of funding, inadequate facilities, absence of IR-related policies, difficulties in collecting content from contributors, copyright concerns, the absence of mandatory self-archiving policies, and a lack of interest from contributors in submitting to IRs. It was

recommended that universities planning to establish IRs should develop comprehensive policies, such that will cover issues on access, content, submission, and preservation policies, to ensure the successful development and management of their repositories.

Akparobore and Omosekejimi (2020) examined awareness and attitude towards the use of IRs by 572 lecturers who are registered library users in seven federal universities in South-South, Nigeria. The findings revealed that the level of awareness of IR by the lecturers is high, and their attitude towards the use of IR was positive. The lecturers used IR for accessing: e-journal articles, e-book collection and e-theses and dissertations for teaching and research; scholarly works to prepare lecture notes; and materials for seminar presentations. Other purpose of use are for depositing scholarly works for safekeeping, developing collaborative workspace/information sharing space, increasing their visibility as authors and researchers and to participate in the scholarly communication process among others.

Methodology

The study adopted a descriptive survey research design of the correlational type. The population of the study comprised all 16,511 postgraduate students in University of Ibadan, Ibadan, Oyo State, Covenant University, Ota, Ogun State and Obafemi Awolowo University, Ile-Ife, Osun State. A two-stage sampling technique was used to select a sample size of 345 postgraduate students. The questionnaire was the data collection instrument and data collected were analysed using frequency count, percentages, mean, standard deviation, correlational and regression analysis.

Result

Types of information resources used in the repositories by the postgraduate students

The types of information resources used in the repositories by postgraduate students in the three universities in Southwestern Nigeria was examined under 10 items with the response scale of: Very Highly Used (VHU), Highly Used (HU), Moderately Used (MU) and Not Used (NU) and shown in Table 1. The result revealed that the types of information resources used most by the respondents are: journal (\bar{x} =3.38), theses and dissertations (\bar{x} =3.19), book chapters (\bar{x} =3.14) and seminar papers (\bar{x} =2.60).

Table 1. Types of information resources used in the repositories by the postgraduate students

S/N	Types of information resources used	VHU		HU		MU		NU		Mean	Std.Dev
		F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%		
1	Patents	21	6.8	77	25.0	124	40.3	86	27.9	2.11	.891
2	Seminar papers	33	10.7	135	43.8	124	40.3	16	5.2	2.60	.748
3	Inaugural lectures	31	10.1	91	29.5	158	51.3	28	9.1	2.41	.791
4	Guest lecture series	14	4.5	74	24.0	153	49.7	67	21.8	2.11	.793
5	Faculty lecture	46	14.9	95	30.8	127	41.2	40	13.0	2.48	.900
6	Conference proceedings	36	11.7	120	39.0	110	35.7	42	13.6	2.49	.871
7	Theses and Dissertations	118	38.3	133	42.2	55	17.9	2	0.6	3.19	.743
8	Book of Abstracts	59	19.2	145	47.1	90	29.2	14	4.5	2.81	.794
9	Journals	155	50.3	120	39.5	29	9.4	4	1.3	3.38	.710
10	Book chapters	106	34.4	143	46.4	55	17.9	4	1.3	3.14	.746
Weighted mean= 2.67 Criterion mean = 2.50											

Frequency of institutional repositories resources used by the postgraduate students

The frequency of institutional repositories resources used by postgraduate students in three universities in southwestern Nigeria, was examined under 10 items, with the response scale of: Daily (D), Weekly (W), Monthly (M), Occasionally (O) and Never (N). Table 2 outlines the frequency of use of IR resources by postgraduate students across three universities in southwestern Nigeria. The weighted mean across all types of IR resources is 3.16, surpassing the criterion mean score of 3.00, indicating an overall high level of usage. Among the most commonly accessed resources are journals ($\bar{x} = 4.11$; Std. dev. = 0.969), book chapters ($\bar{x} = 3.92$; Std. dev. = 1.141), and theses and dissertations ($\bar{x} = 3.72$; Std. dev. = 0.959). In contrast, guest lecture series emerge as the least used resource ($\bar{x} = 2.44$; Std. dev. = 1.112).

The most utilised resources on a daily basis are theses and dissertations (16.9%), weekly are journals, book chapters, seminar papers, and faculty lectures (19.2% to 42.2%). Book of abstracts, conference proceedings, inaugural lectures and patents are used monthly (21.1% and 41.6%) of usage. Resources such as guest lecture series and others are accessed occasionally, with the former having the highest occasional usage at 46.1%.

Table 2: Frequency of IR resources used by the postgraduate students

S/N	Frequency of use of IR resources	D F %	W F %	M F %	O F %	N F %	Mean	Std. Dev	
1	Patents	13 4.2	74 24.0	50 16.2	114 37.0	57 18.5	2.58	1.162	
2	Seminar papers	14 4.5	118 38.3	59 19.2	103 33.4	14 4.5	3.05	1.040	
3	Inaugural lectures	25 8.1	73 23.7	65 21.1	119 38.6	26 8.4	2.84	1.125	
4	Guest lecture series	13 4.2	56 18.2	40 13.0	142 46.1	57 18.5	2.44	1.112	
5	Faculty lecture	51 16.6	59 19.2	40 13.0	124 40.3	34 11.0	2.90	1.301	
6	Conference proceedings	21 6.8	46 14.9	74 24.0	139 45.1	28 9.1	2.65	1.058	
7	Theses & Dissertations	52 16.9	173 56.2	29 16.9	52 16.9	2 0.6	3.72	0.959	
8	Book of Abstracts	43 14.0	128 41.6	60 19.5	71 23.1	6 1.9	3.43	1.051	
9	Journals	124 40.3	130 42.2	21 6.8	30 9.7	3 1.0	4.11	.969	
10	Book chapters	125 40.6	89 28.9	43 14.0	45 14.6	6 1.9	3.92	1.141	
		Weighted mean= 3.16							
		Criterion mean = 3.00							

Purpose of use of IR by the postgraduate students

The result for the purpose of use of IRs by postgraduate students in three universities in southwestern Nigeria is in Table 3. The result revealed that the prominent purpose of use of institutional repositories by the students are: for assignment completion (\bar{x} =3.45), to cite and reference scholarly work (\bar{x} =3.39) and to source for materials for research work (\bar{x} =3.38).

Table 3: Purpose of use of institutional repositories by the postgraduates students

S/N	I use institutional repositories :	SA F %	A F %	D F %	SD F %	Mean	Std. Dev
1	for assignment completion	138 44.8	170 55.2	0 0.0	0 0.0	3.45	.498
2	to source for materials for research	122 39.6	182 59.1	4 1.4	0 0.0	3.38	.513
3	to read articles	113 36.7	176 57.1	19 6.2	0 0.0	3.31	.580
4	to cite and reference scholarly work	134 43.5	164 53.2	6 1.9	4 1.3	3.39	.597
5	to develop collaborative research	108 35.1	178 57.8	20 6.5	2 0.6	3.27	.607
6	to preserve scholarly materials	113 36.7	177 57.5	16 5.2	2 0.6	3.30	.596
7	to peruse the contents from IR	125 40.6	163 52.9	20 6.5	0 0.0	3.34	.596
8	to participate in scholarly communication process	91 29.5	187 60.7	22 7.1	8 2.6	3.17	.665
9	to increase my visibility as an author and researcher	98 31.8	181 58.8	25 8.1	4 1.3	3.21	.639
10	to access materials for seminar presentations	107 34.7	187 60.7	10 3.2	4 1.3	3.29	.591
Weighted mean= 3.31							
Criterion mean = 2.50							

Prevailing Institutional factors to use of IR by the postgraduate students

The institutional factors that could promote the use of institutional repositories by postgraduate students in three universities in southwestern Nigeria, was examined under 13 items, with the response scale of: Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Disagree (D) and Strongly Disagree (SD) and is presented in Table 4. These factors are categorised into Technical Support, Infrastructure, Funding, and Policy with mean scores of 3.65, 2.73, 2.72, and 3.09 respectively, all exceeding the criterion mean score of 2.50 (Table 4). This suggests that the examined institutional factors foster the use of institutional repositories by the students.

Table 4: Prevailing Institutional factors to use of institutional repositories

S/N	Item	SA F %	A F %	D F %	SD F %	Mean	Std. Dev
	Technical support						
1	There is provision of functional helpdesk service for queries on the interface of the IRs	61 19.8	198 64.3	47 15.3	2 0.6	3.03	.614
2	There is training and softskills programmes organised by the institution for the use of IRs	56 18.2	175 56.8	67 21.8	10 3.2	2.90	.722
3	There is necessary software to run and maintain the IRs at all times	58 18.8	144 46.8	96 31.2	10 3.2	2.81	.772
4	There is broadband and network services to use IRs	47 15.3	153 49.7	98 31.8	10 3.2	2.77	.741
Weighted mean: 3.64; Criterion mean: 2.50							
	Infrastructure						
5	There is adequate internet facilities and connectivity within the campus for the use of IRs	51 16.6	140 45.5	108 35.1	9 2.9	2.76	.759
6	There is constant power supply within the campus to enable the use of IRs	48 15.6	127 41.2	116 37.7	17 5.5	2.67	.804
7	There are computer system to enhance the use of IRs	48 15.6	151 49.0	99 32.1	10 3.2	2.77	.746
Weighted mean: 2.73; Criterion mean: 2.50							
	Funding						
8	There is cost associated with submitting research and publications to the IR	24 7.8	196 63.6	82 26.6	6 1.9	2.77	.610
9	There is a required fee and charges for accessing the IR	40 13.0	170 55.2	88 28.6	10 3.2	2.78	.706
10	There is research incentives for student to engage in research and contribute their work	34 11.0	134 43.5	124 40.3	16 5.2	2.60	.752
Weighted mean: 2.72; Criterion mean: 2.50							
	Policy						
11	There is effective policies and regulations in managing and using IRs	101 32.8	161 52.3	40 13.0	6 1.9	3.16	.716
12	There is restriction on the access to use of IRs	54 17.5	165 53.6	89 28.9	0 0.0	2.89	.673
13	There is guidelines and rules for content submission, vetting and reviewing of manuscripts to be accepted in the IRs	113 36.7	157 51.0	34 11.0	4 1.3	3.23	.691
Weighted mean: 3.09; Criterion mean: 2.50; Grand mean: 40.17							

In terms of technical support, respondents generally favoured the provision of functional helpdesk services (\bar{x} : 3.03) and the organisation of training programmes (\bar{x} : 2.90). However, opinions varied regarding the availability of necessary software (mean: 2.81) and broadband/network services (\bar{x} : 2.77). Concerning infrastructure, respondents demonstrated a positive perception of internet facilities (\bar{x} : 2.76) and computer systems (\bar{x} : 2.67) but expressed concerns about consistent power supply (mean: 2.67). Within the funding category, reservations were expressed about associated costs for submitting research (\bar{x} : 2.77) and accessing the repository (\bar{x} : 2.78), although there were indications of research incentives for students (\bar{x} : 2.60). Regarding policy, respondents generally supported the effectiveness of policies and regulations (\bar{x} : 3.16) and the availability of guidelines for content submission (\bar{x} : 3.23). However, concerns were raised about restrictions on access (\bar{x} : 2.89).

Hypothesis

There is no significant relationship between institutional factors and use of institutional repositories by postgraduate students in three universities in southwestern Nigeria

The relationship between institutional factors and use of institutional repositories, was determined using Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC) analysis.

Table 5: Relationship between institutional factors and use of institutional repositories

Variables	N	Mean	Std.Dev	R	P	Remark
Institutional factors	308	2.86	.445	.447	.000	Sig.
Use of institutional repositories	308	3.16	.709			

Table 5 shows the relationship between institutional factors and use of institutional repositories by postgraduate students in three universities in southwestern Nigeria. The result indicated a statistically significant relationship between institutional factors and use of institutional repositories by the postgraduate students ($r = 0.447$, $P < 0.05$). Hence, the Null Hypothesis was rejected.

Discussion of the findings

Types of information resources used in the repositories by the postgraduate students

The study found that journals are the most commonly used information resource. Others include: theses and dissertations, patents, seminar papers and faculty lectures. This finding aligns

with Akparobore and Omoisejimi's (2020) research on the use of Institutional Repositories (IRs) in federal universities in South South, Nigeria. Their study identified various resources within repositories, such as e-journal articles, e-book collections, and electronic theses and dissertations.

Frequency of institutional repositories resources use by the postgraduate students

The findings from this study revealed that the most commonly accessed resources are journals, book chapters and theses and dissertations. In contrast, guest lecture series emerge as the least used resource. The study's findings indicate that journals, book chapters, and theses and dissertations are highly accessed due to their in-depth content, credibility, and easy online availability. They are integral to academic research and often required for academic progression. Conversely, guest lecture series are less utilised, likely because they are less accessible, focus on niche topics, and lack formal academic recognition. This disparity in resource usage underscores the importance of availability and relevance in determining the frequency of use in academic settings. This finding, aligns with that of Bamigbola and Adetimirin (2017), who examined the level of awareness, frequency of use, preferred archiving method, purpose of use of IRs and challenges of use of IRs among lecturers in Nigeria. The findings revealed that majority of the lecturers were aware of IRs, they accessed materials from IRs on daily and weekly basis while they deposited their works into IR on annual and bi-annual basis.

Purpose of use of institutional repositories by the postgraduate students

The prominent purpose of use of institutional repositories by the students, as found by this study, include: for assignment completion, to cite and reference scholarly work, to source for materials for research work, among others. Institutional repositories are highly utilized by students for their comprehensive academic resources, which are crucial for completing assignments, citing scholarly work, and conducting research. Their credibility, ease of access, and support for academic integrity make them indispensable. Additionally, the open access nature of these repositories ensures that all students can use these resources freely, further enhancing their educational experience and supporting their academic endeavors. This finding of this study is again in tandem with that of Bamigbola and Adetimirin (2017) use of IRs among lecturers in Nigeria. The findings revealed that majority of the lecturers used materials from IRs to prepare lecture notes and research works.

Prevailing Institutional Factors to the use of Institutional repositories by the students

The study found technical support, infrastructure, funding, and policy to be the main factors that promote the use of institutional repositories by students. This is supported by Mantikayan and Abdulgani (2018) who averred that institutional factors like training, staff support, technical support and guidance, resources, awards, workload, research culture, tenure and promotion, financial awards, performance standards, peer and social recognition, and leadership factors like appreciation and orientation can influence students' research productivity.

Relationship between institutional factors and use of institutional repositories by the postgraduate students

The study found a statistically significant relationship between institutional factors and use of institutional repositories by postgraduate students. This finding is supported by that of Ogunsola and Oluyemi (2019), who conducted a study on the influence of institutional factors on the Internet use among students' in selected universities in South-West region of Nigeria. The study concluded that institutional factors do make significant contribution to the use of Internet by the respondents of the three selected universities. Similarly, Tony-Okereke (2021) examined institutional factors variable as determinants of lecturers' utilisation of electronic publications in library schools in universities in Nigeria. Findings showed that there is a moderate positive relationship between the institutional factors and lecturers' utilisation of electronic publications.

Conclusion

Institutional repositories play a crucial role in facilitating access to scholarly resources. By providing a centralised platform for archiving and disseminating research outputs, institutions empower postgraduates to share their work with a wider audience. However, institutional factors such as robust technical support, adequate infrastructure, sufficient funding and clear policies contribute significantly to the effectiveness and use of these repositories by postgraduate students.

Recommendations

The following recommendations were made based on the findings of the study:

1. Given that journals, theses, dissertations and book chapters are the most utilised resources, universities should prioritise expanding access to these materials in their institutional

repositories. This could involve increasing the number of subscriptions to relevant journals and actively encouraging faculty to deposit their work.

2. Institutional repositories should be designed to support the primary activities for which students use institutional repositories, such as completing assignments, referencing scholarly work, and sourcing materials for research. This could include creating specialised search functions and user-friendly interfaces that facilitate these activities.
3. To promote the effective use of institutional repositories, university management should provide robust technical support, adequate infrastructure, funding; and clear policies to drive institutional repositories.

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